

Generation of alkoxy sulfonyl radicals from chlorosulfates and their intramolecular capture with alkynes to get sultones

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An unprecedented radical-mediated reaction of alkyne-containing chlorosulfates to synthesize sultones has been established. The reaction implies the formation and subsequent capture of alkoxy sulfonyl radicals, which are species known since long but not studied for synthetic purposes.

The generation and subsequent reactivity of alkyl- and arylsulfonyl radicals ($\cdot\text{SO}_2\text{R}$) have been extensively investigated in the past decades.¹ In contrast, the study of alkoxy sulfonyl radicals ($\cdot\text{SO}_2\text{OR}$) is essentially limited to a work reported in 1989 by C. Chatgililoglu and coworkers (Figure 1a).² Although this pioneer investigation shows that alkoxy sulfonyl radicals can be generated from chlorosulfate derivatives, it is mainly devoted to the study of the absolute rate constants for chlorine abstraction and to the structural characteristics of the alkoxy sulfonyl radicals. However, the reactivity of this type of radicals was not addressed in this original report and, as far as we know, it has not been tackled afterwards.³

initiated our own study. More precisely, we thought that alkyne-containing chlorosulfate derivatives could be ideal systems for this investigation (Figure 1b).⁴ On the one hand, the chlorosulfate functionality could serve as source of the alkoxy sulfonyl radical, and on the other hand, the alkyne functionality could serve as trapping agent for the initially formed radical.⁵ Herein, we disclose the results of this proposal and particularly, we present the first synthetic exploitation of alkoxy sulfonyl radicals generated from chlorosulfate derivatives.

We started our investigation using chlorosulfate derivative **1a** as model substrate (Table 1). For the generation of the alkoxy sulfonyl radical we thought that the desired chlorine abstraction could be achieved with in situ formed silyl radicals.² With all this in mind, we initially studied the reaction of chlorosulfate derivative **1a** with diverse silane derivatives and radical initiators under different reaction conditions (Table 1). As shown, when 1 equivalent of triethylsilane, triphenylsilane or triethoxysilane were added to a 0.1 M solution of chlorosulfate **1a** and the mixture was allowed to react under air atmosphere for 24 hours at room temperature we did not observe any kind transformation (Table 1, entries 1-3). Under the same conditions but using triisopropylsilane, we observed some conversion of the starting material (15%) and we were able to detect the formation of the sultone derivative **2a** (3% yield; Table 1, entry 4). We were pleased to find that the desired process could be promoted more efficiently by using tris(trimethylsilyl)silane (TTMSS)⁶ as the silane counterpart (35% yield of **2a**; Table 1, entry 5). At this point, formation of product **2a** was supposed to proceed by initial generation of the corresponding alkoxy sulfonyl radical and subsequent intramolecular reaction with the alkyne. Considering that these reactions were performed in air, we thought that oxygen and/or light could be the initiators of the radical process. In fact, when the last experiment was performed under argon, using degassed solvent and in the absence of light, we did not observe the formation of **2a** (Table 1, entry 6). Further evidences in favour of a radical mechanism were provided by the experiments performed in the presence of the well-known radical initiator triethylborane (10 mol%).⁷ Thus, the reaction of chlorosulfate **1a** with one equivalent of TTMSS in acetonitrile (0.1 M) at room temperature and in the

a) Alkyl- or arylsulfonyl radicals versus alkoxy sulfonyl radicals

b) Our proposed model to study the generation & capture of alkoxy sulfonyl radicals

Figure 1 Background and our proposal.

Due to this limited knowledge about the chemistry of alkoxy sulfonyl radicals, it seems obvious that new investigations are required. Under these circumstances, we

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presence of triethylborane (10 mol%) resulted in the formation of sultone derivative **2a** (95% conversion, 74% yield) after just 15 minutes (Table 1, entry 7). A somewhat better result (96% conversion, 85% yield) was obtained by adding a slight excess of TTMSS (1.1 equivalents; Table 1, entry 8). Although complete conversion was observed when 1.5 equivalents of TTMSS was used (Table 1, entry 9), under these conditions the yield decreased (69%). Then, for subsequent optimization experiments we used 1.1 equivalents of TTMSS. Finally, the effect of concentration of the reaction was evaluated. By performing the reaction under slightly more concentrated conditions (0.2 M) we obtained the best results (complete conversion and 86% yield for **2a**; Table 1, entry 10).⁸ However, higher concentrations (0.5 M) led to lower yields (61%; Table 1, entry 11).

Table 1. Initial experiments. Screening of silanes, additives and conditions.^a

Ent	Silane	Additive	t	Conv. (%) ^b	Yield (%) ^b
1	Et ₃ SiH (1 equiv.)	-	24 h	-	-
2	Ph ₃ SiH (1 equiv.)	-	24 h	-	-
3	(EtO) ₃ SiH (1 equiv.)	-	24 h	-	-
4	<i>i</i> Pr ₃ SiH (1 equiv.)	-	24 h	15	3
5	TTMSS ^c (1 equiv.)	-	24 h	60	35
6 ^d	TTMSS ^c (1 equiv.)	-	24 h	-	-
7	TTMSS ^c (1 equiv.)	BEt ₃ ^e	15 min	95	74
8	TTMSS ^c (1.1 equiv.)	BEt ₃ ^e	15 min	96	85
9	TTMSS ^c (1.5 equiv.)	BEt ₃ ^e	15 min	100	69
10 ^f	TTMSS ^c (1.1 equiv.)	BEt ₃ ^e	15 min	100	86
11 ^g	TTMSS ^c (1.1 equiv.)	BEt ₃ ^e	15 min	100	61

^a Unless otherwise stated, the reactions were performed at 0.1 mmol scale in acetonitrile (0.1 M) under air atmosphere. ^b Determined by ¹H NMR using 1,4-dinitrobenzene as internal standard. ^c TTMSS = (TMS)₃SiH; tris(trimethylsilyl)silane. ^d Reaction performed under argon atmosphere and in absence of light. ^e 10 mol% of BEt₃ (0.1 M solution in hexanes) was added. ^f Reaction performed at concentration 0.2 M. ^g Reaction performed at concentration 0.5 M

Having identified the conditions shown in Table 1, entry 10 as optimal, we next studied the scope of the transformation using a series of chlorosulfate derivatives **1** containing a terminal alkyne in the structure (Scheme 1). It seems that the reaction is just limited by the accessibility of the starting material. Considering previous works and our own experience,^{2,4,9} chlorosulfates such as **1** derived from primary alcohols fully substituted at β-position are the easiest to synthesize and the most stable. With these starting materials, we obtained the sultone derivatives **2** in high yield in most cases. Particularly remarkable are those reactions performed with chlorosulfate

derivatives containing the alkyne moiety in a remote position. With these reagents, we observed macrocyclization processes that enabled the synthesis of nine- (**2n**) and ten-membered (**2o**) sultone derivatives in an efficient way. It should be noted that in all these reactions implying terminal alkynes, the new bond is established between the sulfur atom and the terminal carbon of the alkyne (*endo* cyclization). The structure of sultone derivative **2d** was unequivocally confirmed by X-ray crystallographic analysis.¹⁰

Scheme 1 Synthesis of sultone derivatives **2** from chlorosulfates **1** containing a terminal alkyne.

Apart from those experiments made with chlorosulfates **1** containing a terminal alkyne, we also performed some experiments with chlorosulfate derivatives **3** containing in their structure an internal alkyne (Scheme 2). Interestingly, in these cases the *exo*-products **4** were obtained.¹¹ Moreover,

formation of the *Z*-alkene seems to be highly favoured (*Z* : *E* > 20:1).

Scheme 2 Synthesis of sultone derivatives **4** from chlorosulfates **3** containing an internal alkyne.

A mechanism that explains the formation of sultone derivatives **2** from alkyne-containing chlorosulfates **1** is the radical chain process shown in Scheme 3a (for simplicity the reaction of chlorosulfate **1a** is taken as model). Initiation would take place by reaction of triethylborane with tris(trimethylsilyl)silane [(TMS)₃SiH; TTMSS] in the presence of oxygen (air atmosphere) to generate the silyl radical **5**.⁷ The propagation phase may start by abstraction of the chlorine atom of chlorosulfate derivative **1a** to form the alkoxysulfonyl radical **6** and tris(trimethylsilyl)chloride.¹² Intramolecular addition of radical **6** to the terminal carbon of the alkyne would generate the new alkenyl radical **7**. This radical species could abstract the hydrogen atom of a new molecule of TTMSS to afford the final product **2a** releasing the silyl radical **3** that may enter another cycle. As shown, the molecule of TTMSS acts as a sacrificial hydrogen atom donor in this sequence.

At this point, it should be noted that at the beginning of our investigation we were concerned about a potential alternative reactivity of our alkyne-containing chlorosulfate derivatives **1**. More precisely, we were aware of the well-known radical-mediated hydrosilylation of alkynes with TTMSS (*anti*-Markovnikov addition).¹³ These reactions imply the formation of the silyl radical **5** and subsequent addition onto the alkyne functionality. However, during our optimization study of the reaction conditions with chlorosulfate derivative **1a**, we never observed the formation of product **8** (or derivatives) coming from the simple hydrosilylation of the alkyne moiety (Scheme 3b). In other words, it seems that once the silyl radical **5** is formed, chlorine abstraction to form the sulfur radical **6** is faster than the alternative direct addition of **5** to the alkyne.

a) Proposed mechanism through a radical chain process

b) Alternative potential reactivity: Hydrosilylation of the alkyne

Scheme 3 Proposed mechanism and alternative reactivity (not observed).

Apart from the new concepts behind the transformation shown in this work, the structure of the products obtained should also be remarked. Thus, sultones, the sulfur analogues of lactones, are very interesting molecular frameworks with applications in several areas.¹⁴ Particularly, α,β -unsaturated sultones such as **2** are valuable synthetic intermediates that may be used, for instance, as dipolarophiles or Michael-type acceptors.¹⁵ As an illustration, we performed the reaction of sultone **2i** with sodium methoxide as a model nucleophile to get the corresponding addition product **9** in 60% yield.

Scheme 4 Synthetic application of α,β -unsaturated sultone **2i**.

In summary, we have discovered a new radical-mediated method to synthesize sultone derivatives from alkyne-containing chlorosulfates. The reaction seems to proceed through the formation of an alkoxysulfonyl radical and its subsequent intramolecular reaction with an alkyne. Although alkoxysulfonyl radicals had been described in a single report long time ago, their reactivity remained unexplored. Then, the work here presented supposes an initial study on the synthetic applications of this type of radicals. This work leaves the door open to investigate new ways of generating alkoxysulfonyl

radicals and to study their reactivity in the presence of different functional groups.

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Conflicts of interest

There are not conflicts to declare.

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